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Moderating Role of Emotional Intelligence on the Relationship between Extraversion Personality Trait and Unethical Aggressive Behaviour among Nigeria Police Officers

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Abstract

Unethical aggressive behaviour is defined as illegal and unlawful attack of suspects and members of the public by Nigeria Police Officers and men. Previous studies have focused on social and administrative unethical behaviour among police while affective aspect of police unethical aggressive behaviour has not been fully explored in research, therefore, this study examines the moderating role of emotional intelligence in the association between extraversion and unethical aggressive behaviour among police officers and men. Multi-stage sampling technique was used to recruit a sample of 391 serving policemen and women (Commissioned and Non-Commissioned) of Nigeria Police Force. Three self-reported measuring instruments were used to generate data from participants. The data were analysed through the use of SPSS version 20 employing hierarchical regression and univariate analysis of variance. The result shows that emotional intelligence contributed a significant portion of changes on unethical aggressive behaviour, likewise extraversion personality trait was found to be responsible for significant portion of variance on unethical aggressive behaviour among Nigeria police officers and men. The interaction of emotional intelligence and extraversion was also found to account for significant variation on unethical aggressive behaviour. Emotional intelligence was observed as a significant moderator of relationship between extraversion and unethical aggressive behaviour. Considering the potential role of emotional intelligence and extraversion in this study, periodic assessment and training on emotional intelligence and extraversion personality trait is recommended for Nigeria police personnel.

Keywords: Emotional intelligence, extraversion personality trait, unethical aggressive behaviour

Introduction

The Nigeria police force (NPF) is law enforcement agency that derives its power and authority from section 124 of the Nigeria constitution (1999 as amended) and constitutionally committed to uphold the Nigeria constitution by maintaining peace, law and order in the society as well as prevention and detection of criminal activities, legal arrest and prosecution of the suspects with

due execution of laws and regulations in accordance with the provision the Nigeria constitution and the police act. Police forces across countries have been traditionally seen as public servants and the front line in criminal justices entrusted and empowered to protect public and oblige justice in which their everyday duties are expected to be mentored by ethics of police profession and personal decision that requires sound judgment (Arzabe & Socci, 2005). However, due to the demanding job and stressful of Police work, aggressive behaviour to pervade police activities in Nigeria and interaction with the public.

Negative emotions such as frustration, anger, stress and use of fear have become a prevalent tool among police officers and men, and if these emotions are not restrained, curtailed or monitored, they could make them susceptible to negative behaviours such as illegal unnecessary force, violating human rights and disrespecting the citizens or suspects. Unethical aggressive behaviour is identified in this study as unwarranted and unlawful torture, beating, kicking and to suspects by members of the Nigeria policemen. It is not uncommon to read about police unethical behaviour in the newspapers. The media coverage gives the impression that unethical aggressive behaviour such as torture, beating, kicking, brutalizing, inhuman behaviour, physical brutalizing attack and insulting suspects and members of the public by the policemen are common and disturbing occurrence in the society. For example, The Punch newspaper of 24th April 2017 reported a photographer that was tortured to death in the police custody. It should be noted that not all police behaviours are unethical or unlawful, but behaviours that deviate from moral acts and can cause pain, injury or harm on suspects are regarded as unethical and unlawful police behaviours and such behaviours are described by Bayley and Garofelo (1997) as overly aggressive behaviours exhibited during the arrest of suspects, control of protest, and following high-speed pursuits by police officers and men. In studying unethical aggressive behaviour among Nigeria police officers and men, it is important to examine factors that are associated with unethical aggressive behaviour. Police officer's personality (like every other citizen) is believed to influenced by contemplation and sensation about whether police job conditions are positive or negative which could influence their professional relationship with others, therefore it is imperative to investigate the influence of personality trait on police unethical aggressive behaviour. The questions about what are the expected personality of policemen generated into what we can be conceived as policemen homogeneous group in term of their characteristics which makes them psychologically different from other occupational groups or from the public. The assertion that policemen possessed similar characteristics inherited in the nature of their job has been fully explained by predisposition and socialization models (Burbeck and Furnham, 1984). Pre-dispositional model hypothesized that some set of people are attracted to policing, while socialization model (McMurrans & McGuire, 2005) postulated that certain social factors interested some in becoming police officers which could modify and shape their characteristics.

Extraversion personality trait as a pleasure in interacting with other members of the society and proneness to sociability characteristics was studied as an independent variable in connection with traffic violation (Renner & Anderle, 2000) and positive correlate was observed between

extraversion and reckless driving. Extraversion was rarely found in literature to show link with anger or aggression, though (Jones, Miller & Lynam, 2011) shows inverse relationship between inwardly-expression of anger and extraversion in conjunction with facet of excitement-seeking having significant relationship with reactive aggression. Similarly, a study by Benfield, Szlemko and Bell (2006) suggested a directional connection between high extraversion and physical aggression in driving, while traffic challenges were found not related to extraversion, while Dahlen and White (2006) study shown that high score on extraversion trait predicted careless driving and proneness to traffic accidents. Based on these there is a prevent idea that extraversion largely contributed to unethical behaviour among police officers. Along these lines one variable suggested to reduce this impact is emotional intelligence as it decreases negative influence of personality on socially exude behaviour such as aggression. Scholars have tried to establish moderating role of emotional intelligence to variables such as counterproductive work behaviours (Yin, 2010), unethical organizational behaviour and job insecurity (Jordan, Ashkanasy & Hartel, 2002), conscientiousness and performance (Douglas, Frink, and Fern, 2004), stress and burnout (Gorgens-Ekermans & Brand, 2012). Bibi, Karim and Sirajuddin (2013) investigated the moderating role of emotional intelligence on work-place incivility and counterproductive work behaviour and negative relationship was observed between emotional intelligence and the counterproductive work behaviour while emotional intelligence moderate workplace incivility and counterproductive work behaviour. Mayer, Salovey and Caruso (2000) also reported negative relationship between emotional intelligence and employees' deviant behaviours. They argue that improvement in employee emotional intelligence reduces deviant behaviours, while a study conducted by Deshpande (2005) was in agreement when suggested that people with higher emotional intelligence consider counterproductive work behaviour more unethical than those who are less on emotional intelligence. Khan (2013) demonstrated positive association between anger and aggressive counterproductive work behaviour and discrete emotion moderated the strength and magnitude of the relationship between injustice and aggressive counterproductive work behaviour. Previous research works have concentrated much on police administrative unethical behaviour associated with corruption, graft for personal interest, embezzlement and social unethical behaviour like sexual misconduct, alcohols related uses, but failed to focus on affective police unethical behaviour, therefore this study tries to bridge the gap in knowledge by studying police unethical aggressive behaviour associated with unlawful treatment of citizen. Therefore, this study examines the moderating role of emotional in the association between extraversion and unethical aggressive behaviour among police officers and men.

Hypothesis

1. Emotional Intelligence will significantly moderate the relationship between extraversion personality trait and unethical aggressive behaviour among Nigeria police officers.

Method

Participants

This study was carried out in Oyo state police command Eleyele, Ibadan. The command has 55 police divisional police headquarters headed by Divisional Police Officers (DPOs) or called station managers, 27 police stations and 15 police post. Oyo state of Nigeria is encapsulated into 33 local governments which cover about 277 square kilometres with Urban, Semi-Urban and rural areas. The participants for this study consist of 391 police officers and men. They were sampled through simple random sampling technique and sample size is justified through Yamane (1972) sample size calculation formula with 95% confidence level was estimated at 391.

Instruments

Unethical aggressive behaviour of the police officers was measure through a 25 items Police Unethical Aggressive Behaviour Scale (Adegbite 2018) rated on five Likert response format ranging from 1= not at all to 5= 5 or more times, and occurring probability scores range from 1 to 125. The scale was validated and Cronbach coefficient alpha of 0.95 was obtained for with (N=391, \bar{x} =68.09, SD=24.79) established as the norm, scores above the standard deviation (SD) of the mean is regarded as high unethical aggressive behaviour, while scores below the standard deviation (SD) of the mean is regarded as low unethical aggressive behaviour.

Extraversion personality trait was measured through 10 items version of personality trait scale (Gosling, Rentfrow & Swann 2003). The response format for the scale range from 1=strongly disagrees to 5=strongly agree. Item 1 and 6 measures extraversion and the author reported the Cronbach alpha of 0.68 for extraversion. The scale was revalidated for cultural adaptation and Cronbach coefficient alpha of 0.72 was obtained for extraversion with (N=391, \bar{x} =6.18, SD=1.55) established as the norm, scores above the standard deviation (SD) of the average mean is regarded as high extraversion personality trait, while scores below the average mean is regarded as low extraversion personality trait.

Police emotional intelligence was measured in this study through adapted 28 items emotional intelligence Appraisal (EIA) scale (Bradberry and Greaves, 2004). The scale measures four areas of emotional intelligence: self-awareness, self-management, social awareness and relationship management. The response format was rated on six-Likert response format ranging from 1=never to 6=always. The scale was revalidated in this study for cultural relativity and Cronbach coefficient alpha of 0.92 was recorded with N=391, \bar{x} =114.56, SD=16.63 established as the norm and score above the standard deviation (SD) of the mean in this study is regarded as high emotional intelligence, while score below the standard deviation (SD) of the average mean is regarded as low emotional intelligence.

Procedure for data collection

Collection of data for this research work involves administration of questionnaires to three hundred and ninety-one (391) randomly selected police officers from Oyo State Commands. Prior to the administration of the instrument, permission was sorted for from the officers and men and they were told the aim of the research. Questionnaires and other writing materials were administered to the selected police officers and the researcher told them that all options are rights, no wrong answer and all responses are going to be accorded with desirable confidentiality. The questionnaires were administered in a sitting arrangement, and they were not allowed to discuss any matter concerning the choice of options on the scale between themselves and the administration of the scale lasted for three days.

Statistical analysis

Data for this study were analysed through hierarchical regression model to test the formulated hypothesis at $p < .05$ level of significance.

Results

Table 1: Summary Table of Pearson Product Moment Correlational Analysis showing relationship between the variables

Variables	1	2	3	Mean	SD	N
UAB	1			49.48	17.84	391
Extra	.39**	1		6.08	1.59	391
EI	-.17**	.28**	1	114.2	15.19	391

**Correlation is significant at 0.01 (1tailed)

Key: UAB=Unethical Aggressive Behaviour, Extra=Extraversion, EI=Emotional Intelligence

Result of the correlation table above shows that extraversion personality trait significantly and positively related with unethical aggressive behaviour. This implies that high score on extraversion personality related to high score in unethical aggressive behaviour. The result further shows that Emotional Intelligence significantly and negatively related to unethical aggressive behaviour, which implies that the higher the emotional intelligence of the police officers involved in this study, the lower their score in unethical aggressive behaviour. The hypothesis stated that Emotional Intelligence will significantly moderate the relationship between extraversion personality trait and unethical aggressive behaviour among Nigeria Police Officers was tested using moderated hierarchical multiple regression analysis and the result presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary table of Hierarchical Regression showing the moderating effect of Emotional Intelligence on the relationship between extraversion and unethical aggressive behaviour

Variables	β	T	R	R ²	ΔR^2	ΔF	P
Step 1			.38	.15	.15	70.98	.000
Gender	-.05	-1.77					.078
Age	-.17	-6.13					.000
Step 2			.39	.16	.01	14.21	.000
Gender	-.03	-1.07					.283
Age	-.18	-6.65					.000
Extra	.10	3.77					.000
Step 3			.42	.18	.02	28.11	.000
Gender	-.03	-1.08					.282
Age	-.19	-6.95					.000
Extra	.11	4.14					.000
EI	-.14	-5.30					.000
Step 4			.48	.24	.06	97.11	.000
Gender	-.01	-.35					.724
Age	-.20	-7.74					.000
Extra	.02	.70					.482
EI	-.31	10.07					.000
EI x Extra	-.32	-9.86					.000

Key: EXTRA = Extraversion,

EI = Emotional Intelligence

IV = Extra;

Moderator = EI;

DV = Unethical Aggressive behaviour,

N = 391

Standardized scores (z-scores) for variables were computed and the variance inflation factors (VIF) tolerance of all component was calculated to control for the presence of multi-collinearity as recommended by Aiken and West (1992) and the result shows absence of multi-collinearity because obtained scores do not reach the critical values usually considered (VIF>10, and tolerance <0.1). Demographic variables of the participants in table 1 above (gender and age) were regressed against unethical aggressive behaviour in the first step of the model as control variables and both gender and age accounted for significant 15% variation on unethical aggressive behaviour, (R²=0.15, p<.01).

In the second step of the model, extraversion personality trait (the predictor variable) was added and regressed against unethical aggressive behaviour (the dependent variable) and the result indicates that extraversion personality trait positively ($\beta=0.10$, $p<.01$) influence unethical aggressive behaviour and significantly accounted for additional 1% variation on unethical aggressive behaviour ($\Delta R^2=0.01$, $p<.01$), therefore, hypothesis two is accepted. Emotional intelligence as the moderator variable was entered in the third step of the model to see the main effect and the result showed that emotional intelligence negatively ($\beta=-0.14$, $p<.01$) influence unethical aggressive behaviour and accounted for significant additional 2% variation to the model ($\Delta R^2=0.02$, $p<.01$).

The interaction term of (Emotional Intelligence X Extraversion Personality trait) was regressed in the fourth step of the model, while gender, age, extraversion personality and emotional intelligence were controlled to determine the moderating interaction effect of emotional intelligence on the relationship between extraversion personality trait and unethical aggressive behaviour. The result shows the moderating interaction effect of extraversion personality trait and emotional intelligence on the changes in unethical aggressive behaviour such that high level of extraversion personality trait combined with low level of emotional intelligence leads to higher level of unethical aggressive behaviour. The interaction regressed in the last step of the model was significant ($\beta=-0.32$, $p<.01$) and explained additional 6% significant variance on unethical aggressive behaviour ($\Delta R^2=0.06$, $P<.001$).

Figure 1: Graphical representation of interaction effect of Extraversion personality trait and Emotional Intelligence on Unethical Aggressive Behaviour.

The figure 1 shows that police officers who are low on emotional intelligence but high on extraversion significantly score high on the mean score of unethical aggressive behaviour. This is followed by police officers low on both emotional intelligence and extraversion, while police officers with both high emotional intelligence and extraversion personality trait significantly score lower on unethical aggressive behaviour.

Discussion

The obtained result of the preceding model revealed significant influence of extraversion personality trait on unethical aggressive behaviour among police. This result implies that extraversion personality trait which is described as outgoing, sociability and lively characteristics has main impact on the police involvement on unethical aggressive behaviour. Some police officers with high extraversion personality may involve in unethical behaviour as a fun of it. It was further discovered that police officers with low extraversion personality trait significantly score low on unethical aggressive behaviour, which means they are lesser involved in unethical aggressive behaviour. This means that officers who are low in sociability, lively and outgoing characteristics are lesser involved in unethical aggressive behaviour. This result suggests pre-assessment of extraversion personality trait for police officers to achieve low involvement in unethical aggressive behaviour. This result was in line with the study conducted by (Renner & Ander, 2000) who suggested positive correlate between extraversion personality and reckless aggressive driving. Similarly, this result corroborates with Benfield, Szlemko and Bell (2006) who found direct connection between high extraversion and physical aggression in driving, while traffic challenges were found not related to extraversion.

The result of the third model revealed a significant influence of emotional intelligence on unethical aggressive behaviour among police. This result means that police involvement on unethical aggressive behaviour influenced by the level of police emotional intelligence. Furthermore, emotional intelligence which described as police officers' ability to understand, recognize, control and manage own's feeling and mood, and that of others and relate well with suspects and citizens has implication for police involvement in unethical aggressive behaviour. The result implies that police officers with high ability to control and manage his/her feeling as well as that of others are regarded as high emotional intelligence police officers and are lesser likely to involved in police unethical aggressive behaviour. Police officers' engagement in unethical aggressive behaviour depends on police level of emotional intelligence. Therefore, if development of police emotional intelligence is given desirable attention, there is tendency to achieve zero tolerance of police unethical aggressive behaviour. This result corroborates with study conducted by Singh (2015) that people with unstable emotions tend to be anxious, depressed and rigid in behaviour, while people who are emotionally stable are found to be more relaxed, quite, tolerate stress and challenges. Also result of Dahlen, Edwards, Tubre, Zyphur and Warren (2011) suggested an inverse association between emotional stability and aggressive driving, disobeying traffic rules and the amount of road accident involved among Canadian drivers while Dahlen and White (2006) supported negative relationship between emotional stability and anger behaviour.

In the last model testing for the moderating effect of emotional intelligence on the relationship between extraversion personality trait and unethical aggressive behaviour among Nigeria police. The result shows a full moderation and a significant interaction effect of emotional intelligence and extraversion personality trait on police unethical aggressive behaviour, therefore. The result

implies that emotional intelligence moderates the main effect of extraversion on unethical aggressive behaviour among police because the knowledge of emotional intelligence reduces the strength of the relationship between extraversion personality trait and unethical aggressive behaviour among police. The plotted graph of the interaction in figure 1 shows that police unethical aggressive behaviour is lower for police officers who reported high extraversion under the condition of low emotional intelligence, but unethical aggressive behaviour is lower for police officers who reported high extraversion under the condition of high emotional intelligence. This means that emotional intelligence ameliorates the relationship between extraversion and unethical aggressive behaviour, if emotional intelligence awareness is given desirable attention among police, it will go a long way to regulate police involvement in unethical aggressive behaviour. Therefore, this result corroborates Rehman, Khalid and Khan (2012) who found the moderating role of emotional intelligence on the relationship between decision-making styles and organisational performance. The result was also in line with Bibi, Karim and Sirajuddin (2013) who suggested moderating role of emotional intelligence on workplace incivility and counterproductive work behaviour, their results were in line with the current study because emotional intelligence emerged as a significant moderator of the relationship between extraversion personality trait and unethical aggressive behaviour.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examines the moderating role of emotional intelligence on the relationship between extraversion and police unethical aggressive behaviour. Data generated were analysed and discussion revealed the following results: Significant main influences of extraversion personality trait and emotional intelligence on unethical aggressive behaviour were statistically observed and the moderating effect of emotional intelligence on the relationship between extraversion personality trait and unethical aggressive behaviour was also observed. Police periodic assessment of emotional intelligence is hereby recommended and must be conducted by psychologist to identify the knowledge of emotional intelligence and to identify those who are high or low on emotional intelligence among police officers. Alongside with this, desirable special attention and creation of awareness and emotional intelligence training is also recommended for police officers and men to enrich their knowledge on emotional intelligence and to achieve zero tolerance of unethical aggressive behaviour in the society. This study recommended pre-assessment and sensitization of police officers on the importance of extraversion personality trait, because unethical aggressive behaviour was found high for officers with high extraversion personality. This study also recommended that people with high emotional intelligence should be considered during police recruitment to achieve zero tolerance for unethical aggressive behaviour. Result of this study provides essential information on the negative facet of unethical aggressive behaviour which is on the rise among policemen. Therefore, it is necessary that emotional intelligence sensitization and extraversion behavioural information is promoted to have ethically minded police officers for effective policing.

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